

Hardware-accelerated Ethernet Interface for Automotive LiDAR Sensors

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Abstract—The automotive industry keeps pushing technology towards fully autonomous vehicles. In the near future, cars are expected to be sufficiently reliable, affordable, and common to simplify several driving tasks. To recreate the surrounding environment in real-time, an autonomous vehicle requires reliable and accurate multi-sensor perception systems, which include RADARs, Cameras, and LiDAR sensors. LiDAR sensors are becoming very popular since they are able to create 2D/3D representations of the car’s vicinity in different light and weather conditions, even at high speeds. However, to achieve high-resolution visualizations, a LiDAR sensor must provide millions of data points to be processed, which often requires powerful processing systems. With this article, we propose an accelerated interface for LiDAR sensors composed of a data packet decoder and a reconstruction system, fully deployed on an embedded reconfigurable hardware platform with field-programmable gate array (FPGA) technology. The proposed FPGA-based solution is able to interface different LiDAR sensors at the same time, outperforming software-only approaches by reaching lower latency and high performance results.

Index Terms—*Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA)*, *light detection and ranging (LiDAR)*, *Data Decoding*.

I. INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is putting several efforts into developing and deploying fully autonomous vehicles in the very near future. Optimists predict that by 2030 autonomous vehicles will be sufficiently reliable, affordable, and widely spread on our public roads, replacing many current human driving tasks [1]. However, most vehicles today are still manually controlled, and to achieve fully autonomous features, a vehicle must go through different levels of automation. For instance, the society of automotive engineers (SAE) [2] defines six automation levels, where SAE-levels 0, 1, and 2 require the driver to actively monitor the driving activities, with the SAE-levels 3, 4, and 5, the automated vehicle must be able to monitor and navigate the environment without the driver’s interaction. To make this possible, an autonomous vehicle requires reliable multi-sensor perception systems equipped with RADARs, Cameras, and LiDAR sensors [3,4].

Although the adoption of LiDAR sensors in the automotive industry is relatively new, they are assumed as a key technology for the future of autonomous driving due to their ability to recreate the surroundings of the car through a high-resolution 2D/3D point cloud representation [5]. LiDAR sensors can be used to assist the perception system in several important tasks such as in obstacles, objects, and vehicles detection [6]–

[8]; pedestrians recognition and tracking [9,10]; road filtering [11]; among others [12]. Despite the success of LiDAR in these applications, there are still several challenges that must be tackled, such as mutual interference [13,14], adverse weather [15]–[17], and high data throughput. For instance, the Velodyne VLS-128, one of the best LiDAR sensors currently available in the market, can produce up to 9.6M points/second. Because an autonomous vehicle can be equipped with more than one sensor, even from different manufacturers [3,18,19], handling the heterogeneity of their data output can be even more challenging [20].

To mitigate the integration with the perception system, manufacturers usually provide software packages to interface their sensors. However, the processing system still needs to deal with the huge amount of data they generate in real-time. Current solutions to tackle this issue include compression methods before data being transferred to a processing unit [21,22]. Despite presenting good results, the compression tasks can add significant processing overhead, which may heavily penalize real-time applications that rely on the LiDAR output [23]. Other approaches attempt to solve this problem by providing low-level interfaces for LiDAR packet decoding and data reconstruction [24]–[28]. Although providing promising results, these approaches are tailored for only one sensor model, either providing support only in software or through a custom-made System-on-Chip (SoC) device.

With this work, we present a hardware-based data packet decoder that can drive LiDAR sensors with an Ethernet interface. By decoding LiDAR data in hardware, our solution can efficiently handle the high data throughput of a LiDAR, even in a multi-sensor configuration. The solution also includes a data reconstruction module that transforms the received data into a custom representation, supporting different sensor models and data outputs. The main contributions of this article are summarized as follows: (1) a hardware-accelerated data packet decoder to interface sensors with an Ethernet port; (2) a coordinate system module that converts data to different coordinate representations; (3) the support for Hokuyo LiDAR sensors; and the evaluation of the proposed system.

II. AUTOMOTIVE LiDAR SENSORS: BACKGROUND

The output of a LiDAR sensor is a point cloud that contains a set of points in space, recreating objects in the vehicle’s vicinity. To create high-resolution representations of these

objects, high-grade sensors output millions of points/second, providing real-time data in a wide field of view (FoV) at high frame rates. Additionally, some sensors feature high-range capabilities, further increasing the data throughput requirements. As a consequence, sensors must implement high bandwidth interfaces capable of handling hundreds of Mb/s to deliver data to the processing system, which will receive, decode, and process the point cloud in real-time.

A. Sensor interfaces

Most LiDAR sensors used in automotive applications use Controller Area Network (CAN) buses and Ethernet interfaces. CAN is an automotive field bus-level communication standard that enables real-time message exchange between a computing system and devices. It includes built-in error detection, high degrees of robustness, and extensive flexibility features. Nonetheless, the CAN bus only supports data rates up to 1 Mb/s [29], restricting its utilization to sensors with low resolutions, limited FoV, and short-range capabilities.

Ethernet is a family of wired networking technologies widely used in automotive for data transmission by multimedia and infotainment systems [30]. Despite standard Ethernet networks only reaching 10 Mb/s, recent versions have increased the transfer rate to speeds above 100 Mb/s, meeting the high-bandwidth requirements.

LiDAR sensors output data using the User Datagram Protocol (UDP) or the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) and usually provide an HTTP-based interface for the configuration and management operations. However, the data packet layout is still manufacturer-defined, which requires specific data decoding and reconstruction.

B. LiDAR Output

Fig. 1. Spherical coordinate system used by a LiDAR sensor.

Each point in the point cloud can store precise information about several measured/calculated properties, including point coordinates, target reflectivity, timestamps, and much more. The coordinate systems used to represent a point's position in the point cloud are usually the cartesian and the spherical systems. In the cartesian system, a point is defined by (x, y, z) coordinates, which are easy to manipulate and commonly used by point cloud processing algorithms. In the spherical coordinate system, a point is defined by a radius r (distance), elevation ω (vertical angle), and azimuth α (horizontal angle), as depicted by Figure 1. This representation is mainly adopted in the LiDAR output since it can reduce the amount of data to

be transmitted, i.e., the elevation and azimuth can be inferred by the point's position inside a packet, eliminating the need to transmit these values.

Since the cartesian coordinate system is the preferred representation for point cloud processing, sensor manufacturers deploy in their software drivers the conversion from the spherical data to the cartesian coordinates (Equations 1, 2, and 3). However, a single point cloud can hold thousands of points, and converting each point using software libraries can cause a significant processing overhead. This penalty can be further increased when the perception system includes a multi-sensor configuration with sensors from different manufacturers.

$$x = r \times \cos \omega \times \sin \alpha \quad (1)$$

$$y = r \times \cos \omega \times \cos \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$z = r \times \sin \omega \quad (3)$$

III. HARDWARE-ACCELERATED LiDAR INTERFACE

To address the aforementioned challenges, this work proposes ALFA-Pi, a hardware-accelerated data packet decoding and reconstruction system for automotive LiDAR sensors.

A. System Architecture

Fig. 2. ALFA-Pi system architecture.

The ALFA-Pi architecture (Figure 2) is mainly composed of a software and a hardware layer. To cope with these requirements, ALFA-Pi was built upon the hardware platform ZCU104 Evaluation Kit. This platform features the Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC, which includes two distinct systems, the processing system (PS) and the programmable logic (PL) with FPGA technology. Additionally, the ALFA-Pi includes the EVAL-CN0506-FMCZ expansion board. This board is a dual-channel, low latency, low power Ethernet PHY card that supports 10 Mbps, 100 Mbps, and 1000 Mbps speeds for industrial Ethernet applications, enabling the deployment of hardware peripherals that collect and process LiDAR data.

The PL system features several hardware blocks: the *Ethernet Interface System*, the *Sensor Packet Decoder*, and the *Coordinate Systems Converter (CSC)*, which are responsible for the reading, decoding, and reconstruction of LiDAR data, respectively. They communicate using the advanced extensible interface (AXI)-4 bus, allowing high-performance memory accesses, high-speed point cloud data streaming, and small control/configuration operations. On the other hand, the PS

side features an embedded Linux distribution running a **ROS environment**, which allows for the real-time LiDAR data acquisition and the control/configuration of the hardware functionalities through the developed ALFA-Pi ROS Package.

B. Ethernet Interface System

The **Ethernet Interface System** is responsible for the direct reading of Ethernet data from the EVAL-CN0506-FMCZ board without the intervention of the operating system (OS). This device resorts to Xilinx intellectual property (IP) cores, such as the ADIN1300 and the AXI 1G/2.5G Ethernet Subsystem, to implement the physical (PHY) and the media access controller (MAC) layers, respectively. The remaining layers of the communication stack, e.g., the transport layer, are still controlled by the OS network stack manager as the hardware does not require them to extract LiDAR data from packets. Finally, after performing all MAC-related operations, e.g., flow control and data frame integrity, the **Sensor Packet Decoder** collects data through an AXI4-Stream interface and starts the filtering and decoding tasks, according to the sensor(s) connected to the ALFA-Pi.

C. Sensor Packet Decoder

Fig. 3. Sensor Packet Decoder block diagram.

The **Sensor Packet Decoder** (Figure 3), is responsible for the high-speed processing and decoding of the received data. It is composed of two main blocks: (1) the **Packet Filter** that is responsible for filtering the received Ethernet data; and (2) the **Sensor Interfaces** module, which contains sensor-specific interface blocks responsible for the high-speed decoding of LiDAR data according to their model/version. The **Packet Filter** features several operations that allow filtering tasks at different layers of the network stack, e.g., IPV4 addresses, TCP/UDP protocol. When the received packet belongs to a supported sensor, it is forwarded to its corresponding sensor interface block, otherwise, it is rejected. Additionally, this module's registers and configuration parameters can be customized in run-time using the ALFA-Pi ROS package.

The **Sensor Interfaces** block contains several sensor-specific hardware modules, each of them responsible for the decoding tasks of the corresponding sensor model/version. This building block approach facilitates the support of new LiDAR sensors since it only requires the development of new modules when a new sensor is added. One of the main goals of ALFA-Pi is to support several sensors connected simultaneously. Thus, the **Sensor Packet Decoder** features

a multiplexing system that combines all sensors data into a single point cloud stream in the (custom) ALFA-Pi's data format. At the current stage of development, the **Sensor Interfaces** module only supports LiDAR sensors from Hokuyo. However, hardware modules to support sensors from other manufacturers, e.g., Velodyne, are currently being added.

Hokuyo Sensors Support

From Hokuyo's portfolio, ALFA-PI supports sensors that use an Ethernet interface and the SCIP2.0 (Sensor Communication Interface Protocol) protocol to transmit their ranging data. Figure 4 depicts the SCIP2.0 data layout mainly adopted by Hokuyo sensors according to their operation mode and application. This protocol is based on a command-response principle, where the sensor responds according to the commands/requests performed by the host system. The data is structured in blocks of 64 bytes, which contain character encoded data point information followed by a check code (CC) character for error detection. Finally, it is possible to infer the azimuth information for each data point using its position inside the message.

Fig. 4. Hokuyo packet format. (Check Code (CC), Response Delimiter (RD))

The SCIP2.0 format requires several TCP packets to send a single message (containing an entire point cloud frame). Thus the Hokuyo Sensor Interface block features sensor-specific data buffers to store multiple TCP packets. Although this approach can lead to higher hardware resource consumption, it highly improves the performance of the decoding operation. The Hokuyo module features a message controller to forward data to each sensor-specific buffer, detect the reception of an entire frame, and to trigger the decoding task. Finally, the output of this module is a data frame that follows the custom ALFA-Pi's data format.

D. ALFA-Pi Data Format

One of the main features of ALFA-Pi is the ability to interface multiple sensors, even from different models. For this reason, and to provide enough abstraction to the upper framework layers, the data output from the **Sensor Packet Decoder** block follows a custom data format, which can hold information for both 2D and 3D sensors, also supporting sensors with multiple return capabilities.

Figure 5 depicts the data structure of the ALFA-Pi frame format. It starts with the **Flags** field, which indicates when a new frame starts, and the **Sensor ID**, which holds the sensor

identification. The following fields contain the *Azimuth* (16-bit) and the *Vertical Angle* (16-bit), followed by the distance values *D0* and *D1*, each requiring 20 bits. Both *D0* and *D1* contain the point’s distance obtained by the sensor (in millimeters) for each return. Finally, the *Extra 0* and *Extra 1* fields, 8 bits each, can hold extra information about other sensor-specific features, e.g., reflectivity.

Fig. 5. ALFA-Pi spherical system representation (96 bit).

E. Coordinate Systems Converter module

The *Coordinate Systems Converter (CSC)* module is responsible for converting the sensor data between the spherical and cartesian coordinate systems. Because these conversions when performed in software cause several processing overheads, the ALFA-Pi deploys them in dedicated hardware accelerators. There are two hardware-based techniques to perform such calculations, the CORDIC algorithm or by resorting to look-up tables (LUTs) with pre-calculated values. Despite being more resource-consuming, the *CSC* module follows the LUTs approach, which allows for better performance results.

The ALFA-Pi’s LUTs implementation resorts to a block RAM (BRAM) memory and uses a table/array of already computed sine and cosine values, turning the run-time computation into a simple indexing operation. This allows for a significant processing time reduction since retrieving the value from memory is faster than its recurring computation. The sine and cosine values used for populating these tables were calculated using the C math library with a resolution of 0.01° for angles between 0° and 90°, storing five decimal digits for each computed value. When high-level applications require the point cloud in the cartesian representation, the *CSC* module receives the output of the ALFA-Pi system and converts the spherical coordinates into a cartesian system, as depicted in Figure 6. The only difference between both packet formats is the coordinate representation and size, whereas the cartesian format requires 120 bits to store the (x, y, z) values.

Fig. 6. ALFA-Pi cartesian system representation (120 bit).

IV. EVALUATION

The evaluation of the ALFA-Pi consists of comparing a software-based LiDAR setup (native ROS driver; software-based Ethernet port; Linux network stack; with no acceleration support) with a hardware-based setup (hardware Ethernet port; modified network stack/interface; ALFA-Pi hardware modules). All software runs on top of an embedded Linux (5.4-xilinx-v2019.2) with a ROS environment (Ros1 melodic distribution). The hardware platform remains the ZCU104 Evaluation Kit and the EVAL-CN0506-FMCZ Ethernet board, with the CPU operating at 1.2 GHz and the FPGA fabric running at a clock speed of 100 MHz.

A. Network Interface

To test the impact of adding the hardware Ethernet connector, we ran the iPerf3 tool on the embedded Linux, using the client-server test application to evaluate the most important metrics of both UDP and TCP data streams in three different configurations: (1) native Ethernet port on the ZCU104 Evaluation Kit; (2) hardware Ethernet interface on the EVAL-CN0506-FMC card; and (3) hardware Ethernet interface EVAL-CN0506-FMC with ALFA-Pi accelerators. In all configurations, the network stack is managed by the Linux network manager. The embedded platform was connected to a desktop Linux host through a 1 Gbit/s Ethernet interface.

Table I summarizes the gathered results. Each of the three configurations achieved a maximum TCP bandwidth of roughly 941 Mbit/s, and a maximum UDP bandwidth of nearly 955 Mbit/s. TCP retries are always zero, while the Packet Loss ratio in the UDP tests remained as low as 0.002%. On both TCP and UDP tests, the Jitter is always 0.018 milliseconds (ms). With these results from iPerf3, we can conclude that adding the hardware-based network interface and the ALFA-Pi accelerators has no effect on the network behavior at the application layer.

TABLE I
NETWORK PERFORMANCE RESULTS FROM IPERF.

Test		Native Ethernet	Hardware Ethernet	ALFA-Pi
TCP	Bandwidth (Mbits/s)	941.243	941.904	941.302
	Retries	0	0	0
UDP	Bandwidth (Mbits/s)	955.937	955.929	955.971
	Packet Loss (%)	0.002	0.001	0.002
	Jitter (ms)	0.018	0.018	0.018

B. Performance Evaluation

The performance results can be highly dependent on the sensor’s type, manufacturer, and model, as these variables can affect the behavior of the ALFA-Pi’s sensor block used in the packet decoding task. In this evaluation, we have created microbenchmarks for different setups: (1) a software-based solution with the native sensor’s ROS driver using the hardware platform (without ALFA-Pi) connected to a Hokuyo sensor; (2) a software-based solution with the ALFA-Pi accelerators (including the *CSC* block for the conversion between different coordinate systems) and the ALFA-Pi ROS driver; (3) and the

full ALFA-Pi hardware solution connected to other hardware accelerators, also available in the FPGA, that deploy high-level application tasks. For instance, in this last setup, the ALFA-Pi can provide the received and processed point cloud frames directly to other hardware blocks, e.g., for point cloud weather denoising [17], avoiding the communication with high-level applications that usually perform such processing in software. For a fair comparison, we used the same point cloud data (raw Ethernet packets captured from the sensor output) on both native and ALFA-Pi setups.

Native ROS driver vs. ALFA-Pi driver

After the Ethernet interface receives the point cloud data, the native ROS sensor’s driver reads it from the Linux network stack layer, reconstructs the point cloud in software using the cartesian coordinates system, and makes it available to other applications by publishing into a ROS topic. In contrast, the ALFA-Pi hardware reads sensor data directly from the Ethernet interface, decodes data packets according to the sensor’s model, and reconstructs the point cloud using the CSC hardware block. Finally, data is sent to the available DDR4 memory, which can be accessed from the ALFA-Pi software driver in the PS.

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF THE NATIVE IMPLEMENTATION VS. ALFA-Pi ROS DRIVER AND ALFA-Pi HARDWARE.

Sensor	Point Cloud Size	Native ROS driver (ms)	ALFA-Pi driver (ms)	Gain ₁	ALFA-Pi hw (ms)	Gain ₂
UST-10LX (Distance)	1081	2.642	0.0435	60.73x	0.032	81.55x
UST-10LX (Distance+Intensity)	1081	2.647	0.0759	34.87x	0.064	40.86x

Table II depicts the collected results from using the Hokuyo sensor in both Distance and Distance+Intensity operation modes, generating a point cloud size of 1081 points per frame. Regarding the Hokuyo native ROS driver, it requires approximately 2.642 ms to process a point cloud frame when the sensor outputs only the point’s coordinates (horizontal angle and distance) and 2.647 ms when the intensity values are added to the packet. When using the hardware *Sensor Packet Decoder* and the *CSC* module with the ALFA-Pi ROS driver, the proposed setup requires 0.0435 ms to process one point cloud frame, representing a performance gain (column Gain₁) up to nearly 60x when the sensor operates in the Distance mode, and 0.0759 ms (34x of performance gain) when the sensor’s output includes the Distance+Intensity values. The difference between these performance gains is mainly related with the number of packets that are sent by the sensor when operating in the Distance+Intensity mode, which is almost twice the packets when the sensor only outputs data in the Distance mode. When the output of ALFA-Pi is directly connected to other hardware accelerators, the performance gains in processing a complete point cloud frame can be further improved (column Gain₂). This is caused by the reduced number of memory accesses required when the point cloud is processed by software-based applications.

C. Hardware Resources

All ALFA-Pi features come at the cost of FPGA resources, which vary according to the number of sensors connected to the system. Table III summarizes all the required FPGA elements (from the available in the Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC) in terms of LUTs, look-up table random access memories (LUTRAMs), Flip-Flops (FFs), and BRAMs, for the deployment of *Hokuyo Interface* block, the *Packet Filter* module, the *CSC* block, and the *Hardware Ethernet* interface. Each module was evaluated separately, since different ALFA-Pi settings and modifications will result in different resource utilization. Since ALFA-Pi can interface sensors in a multi-sensor configuration, we also evaluate the required hardware for a different number of connected sensors.

TABLE III
HARDWARE RESOURCES UTILIZATION.

	Sensors	LUTs (230400)	LUTRAMs (101760)	FFs (460800)	BRAMs (312)
Hardware Ethernet	-	4683 (2.03%)	556 (0.546%)	9213 (2%)	5.5 (1.76%)
Packet Filter	1	107 (0.046%)	0 (0%)	262 (0.057%)	0 (0%)
	2	218 (0.095%)	0 (0%)	334 (0.072%)	0 (0%)
	4	264 (0.12%)	0 (0%)	427 (0.093%)	0 (0%)
	8	358 (0.16%)	0 (0%)	612 (0.13%)	0 (0%)
	16	567 (0.25%)	0 (0%)	981 (0.21%)	0 (0%)
Hokuyo Interface	1	196 (0.085%)	16 (0.016%)	421 (0.091%)	2 (0.64%)
	2	316 (0.14%)	16 (0.016%)	514 (0.11%)	5 (1.6%)
	4	490 (0.21%)	16 (0.016%)	700 (0.15%)	10 (3.2%)
	8	865 (0.38%)	16 (0.016%)	1072 (0.23%)	20 (6.4%)
	16	1586 (0.68%)	16 (0.016%)	1816 (0.39%)	40 (12.82%)
CSC	-	1350 (0.58%)	0 (0%)	57 (0.012%)	17 (5.45%)

The *Ethernet Interface System* was deployed straight out of the box and does not feature any customization parameters. Therefore, each Ethernet port requires 4683 LUTs, 556 LUTRAMs, 9213 FFs, and 5.5 BRAMs, regardless of the number of sensors connected. Regarding the *Sensor Packet Decoder* block, which includes the *Packet Filter* and at least one sensor interface, it can present different configurations regarding the number of sensors connected to the system. For the most resource-demanding test scenario, i.e., connecting 16 sensors to the system, the resource requirements are kept as low as 567 LUTs, 981 FFs, and zero LUTRAMs and BRAMs units. These resources are not affected by the type/model of the sensor.

The *Hokuyo Sensor Interface* highly depends on the number of sensors connected to ALFA-Pi. This is mainly due to the storage resources required in the packet reconstruction process since there is the need to store multiple TCP packets simultaneously. Therefore, the most critical resource is the required number of BRAMs (the scarcest resource in the hardware platform) used to accommodate the received Hokuyo packets, which exponentially increases when the number of connected sensors increases. Connecting 16 Hokuyo sensors would require 1586 LUTs, 16 LUTRAMs (this value never changes), 1816 FFs, and 40 BRAMs. The *CSC* module is responsible for performing the fast conversion between the two coordinate systems used in ALFA-Pi. Since it uses LUTs to immediately find the corresponding (x, y, z) values of a point

inside multiple tables stored in BRAMs, it requires 1350 LUTs and 17 BRAMs, being the LUTRAMs, and FFs as low as 0 and 57, respectively.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The adoption of LiDAR sensors in the automotive industry is growing at a breathtaking pace. Current perception systems based on multi-sensor approaches, which some include several LiDAR sensors, can get more accurate readings of the vehicle's surroundings but require more processing power to handle the high volume of point clouds generated by several sensors working at the same time. Motivated by this trend, this article proposes a hardware-based solution for packet decoding and data reconstruction, which contrarily to other state-of-the-art solutions, can support different sensors connected via an Ethernet interface. The performed evaluation shows that ALFA-Pi can achieve good performance gains compared with the sensor's native software-only ROS-based solution. Despite APFA-Pi only providing support for Hokuyo sensors, we are currently working on adding support for the Velodyne sensor's portfolio, one of the biggest players in the LiDAR market.

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